

QUIZ**LAST NAME: IDIM****FIRST NAME: ESSIEN****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **If you have a colon in the middle of a sentence, and what follows after is a quotation or multiple sentences, what is the Turabian rule of style guide regarding the first word after the colon?**
 - The first word must be sentence spaced.
 - Indent the first word.
 - Capitalize the first word.¹**
 - There must be a comma before the first word.

¹ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertation: Chicago style for Students & Researchers*. Eighth edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press (2013) 300- 301.

2. **A typical quotation is enclosed in a double quotation mark and, is part of a sentence within a paragraph. However, a quotation that takes up more than five lines be formatted as a block quotation rather than a regular quotation. However, most of the standard rules for quotation will still apply. Which of the following will be an exception?**
- Enclosed with quotation marks.
 - It will begin as part of a paragraph.
 - In text-citation will come before the ending punctuation mark.²**
 - In text-citation will come after the ending punctuation mark
3. **Success as a researcher does not only depend on how information is gathered and analyzed but it also depends on one of the following.**
- How the researcher collated the information.
 - How the researcher synthesized the information.
 - How clearly you report your reasoning.³**
 - How clearly you can convince your reader.

² Turabian, A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertation: Chicago style for Students & Researchers, 349.

³ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications (2008), 6.

4. **For the purpose of seeking a topic and successfully completing a dissertation, the focus should be on one of the following.**

- Creating an original work.
- Contributing to an existing body of knowledge.
- Replicating a previous study or aspect of it.
- Sound topic that is clear and concise.⁴**

5. **The methodology paragraph of a dissertation will not include.**

- Overview of the research design.
- Proposed research sample.
- How to deal with the issue credibility and reliability.
- The research conceptual framework.⁵**

6. **The data analytical sequential phases include one of the following.**

- Coding the data.⁶**
- Summarizing the data.
- Data collection sequencing.
- Interpreting the data.

⁴ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 32.

⁵ *Ibid.*, 45.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 118.

7. **One of the following is a major source of data needed for understanding a phenomenon under study in a qualitative research.**
- Questionnaire.
 - Interview.**⁷
 - Diaries, personal letters, and correspondence.
 - Autobiographies and memoirs.
8. **Style is very important when writing EUCLID dissertation, which one of the following style guides in a series permits the placement of an additional comma before the last ‘and,’ and also before ‘etc.’**
- Turabian Style Guide.
 - APA.
 - English Style Guide.**⁸
 - Chicago Rules

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 120.

⁸ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, seventh edition (2011), 20- 21.

9. **When colons are used, there is no requirement for the next word to begin with a capital letter. The following statement is true for one of the following.**

Turabian Style Guide.

APA.

English Style Guide⁹

Chicago Rules

10. **The use of single quotes is standard and double quotes inside, and punctuation always follows the outside of the closing quote. Besides, open and close quotation marks must always take any period or comma that is part of the quote. The statement is in contrast to one of the following.**

English Style Guide.

Turabian.¹⁰

APA.

W.H.O Rule Book.

⁹ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, English Style Guide, 20.

¹⁰ Ibid.

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